

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF JUGLOTE-SKARDU ROAD (JSR) ON MARGINALIZED COMMUNITIES

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Abstract

Background: The transport sector is an important component of the economy impacting development and the welfare of the people. When transport infrastructure is efficient, it provides various economic and social opportunities and benefits that result in positive multiplier effects such as better accessibility to markets, employment, education, health, and additional investments. **Objectives:** The research intends to analyze the pre and post-social and cultural impact of JSR and to assess the economic impact of JSR on the community. **Methods:** To have an insight of local's perception a structured questionnaire is used to collect the primary data from the field. The sample size was 100 respondents including both the male and female adults. The questionnaire comprises both the open ended and close ended questions which are then analyzed statistically. **Results:** The results show the social, economic and cultural changes in the study area due to the Juglote-Skardu road, Almost 81 % of the respondents agreed that this project has positive impacts in terms of increasing income and economic activities in the area. 89 % of the respondents agreed that the project would also have an impact on the cultural perspectives of the residents. About 97% of the local community believes that the reduction in travelling time to other cities of Pakistan due to this project will help in increasing tourists' influx and other economic opportunities. **Conclusions:** This study found that JSR is regarded as a means of socio-economic development. The expansion of JSR has contributed to an increase in mobility while reducing the distance to destinations, travel costs, and travel time.

INTRODUCTION

The construction of suitable communication infrastructure is an essential aspect of regional development (Yasin & Qasim, 2020). The primary objective is to establish the fundamental conditions required for the overall development of the socioeconomic system and other economic components (Prus and Sikora, 2021). From an economic perspective, the key aspect of transport infrastructure lies in its public nature, as it offers services that have a significant impact on the economy and society as a whole. By facilitating the movement of people and goods, plays a crucial role in

creating favorable conditions for economic activities (Mendy et al., 2009). An appropriately developed transport infrastructure can have a stimulating effect on a specific area, fostering increased economic activity and enhancing competitiveness within the surrounding environment. This is especially evident at the regional level, where the quality of road infrastructure and its alignment with major communication arteries play a significant role (Bojar et al., 2013; Raje, 2007). According to Thacker et al. Ali (2019), infrastructure has a direct or indirect

impact on the achievement of all Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Assessing the social and cultural impacts of transportation systems is challenging due to the inherent variability in social environments and the diverse interpretations of social change. The level of anticipation and the resilience of the affected population also play a significant role in shaping these impacts (Ibrar et al., 2022). The construction of highways is considered the basic means of modern communication and transportation systems as they play a vital role in the economic development and well-being of a nation. Transport corridors financially affect the existence of the adjacent communities. Different scientists have worked on the effects of transportation on the local community (Tanga, 2014; Asomani, 2015). These highways channel resources into energetic areas like trade, roads, exchange, energy, and media communication for economic development and growth (Ramachandran, 2011). Experts and policymakers in the field of transportation have endorsed the idea that local support is tied to financial effects (Farooq et al., 2023). The impact of Juglote-Skardu Road (JSR) on neighboring areas has not been analyzed so far. Nevertheless, JSR, the strategic vein and lifeline of Baltistan has come to life providing the region with better tourism and economic potential a gateway to mountaineering expeditions (Qasim et al., 2022) in the Karakorum Range, including the mighty K2, Gasherbrum-I, Gasherbrum-II, and Broad peak. In this paper, we have examined the structural significance of transport infrastructure on the social and economic condition of the local community (Yoon, 2001).

Highways are considered the basic means of modern communication and transportation systems as they play a vital role in the economic development and well-being of a nation. Transport corridors financially affect the existence of the adjacent communities. Different scientists have worked on the effects of transportation on the local community (Tanga, 2014; Asomani, 2015). These highways channel resources into energetic areas like trade, roads, exchange, energy, and media communication for economic development and growth (Ramachandran, 2011). Experts and policymakers in the field of transportation have endorsed the idea that local

support is tied to financial effects. The impact of Juglote-Skardu Road (JSR) on neighboring areas has not been analyzed so far. JSR, the strategic vein and lifeline of Baltistan has come to life providing the region with better tourism and economic potential and is a gateway to mountaineering expeditions in the Karakorum Range, including the mighty K2, Gasherbrum-I, Gasherbrum-II, and Broad peak. While transport scholars and strategy makers have endorsed that local individual, support is tied to financial effects, the production outcome of JSR on neighborhood individuals has not been analyzed.

In this paper, the structural significance of transport infrastructure's effect on Social and Economic on the total impact on local individuals' support for the improvement of the area was examined (Yoon, 2001). Road and transport infrastructure is a way for the development of economically marginalized regions by focusing on investment in essential areas like roads, energy, trade, and communication which are crucial factors for development (Ramachandran and Linde, 2011). JSR is one of the biggest projects in Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) and the local people have many expectations from it (Qasim et al., 2024). The main objective of this project is to boost the economy of GB and give infrastructural and social development to GB. It will also increase trade volume with other provinces of Pakistan and China (Ali et al., 2016; Ali et al., 2017; Anwar & Qasim, 2024). JSR is very important from a business, tourism, and strategic point of view. It connects the Baltistan region with the Gilgit region through the Karakoram Highway (KKH) and is considered one of the biggest infrastructural projects witnessed in the history of GB.

2. Research Methodology

Perception of the local community was gathered using a structured questionnaire including both quantitative and qualitative questions in the areas connected with Juglote-Skardu Road (JSR). Multiple indicators were used to measure the perceived impact of JSR to improve the validity and reliability of the data while minimizing errors. The unacceptable items were eradicated for further analysis. Data were collected from 100 respondents through a questionnaire and were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

2.1 Sampling design and survey

A total number of 100 respondents including both male and female were randomly selected from different work groups including local businesses, agriculture, entrepreneurs, civil society, and students. All the respondents surveyed were adults (18 years + age).

2.2 Study area

The Baltistan region of Gilgit-Baltistan is also known as Little Tibet. The Northeastern region of Baltistan houses almost one-fourth population of the Gilgit Baltistan region (Qasim et al., 2023). This road was started in 1982 and took twelve years the complete, costing the loss of precious lives which made it even costlier. Even after the completion of the project, the road remained infamous due to the tardiness of the workforce and frequent disasters including landslides. The current extension of JSR has been made after 40 years of its first-ever construction through the highest standard highways. This strategic highway built across the serrated extend has opened many ways to boost the economic potential of the region. Gilgit Baltistan has been recording a substantial flow of tourists in the region (Qasim et al., 2024). Juglote-Skardu Road is powered to provide the region with better tourism activities, boost economic potential to the maximum, and improve strategic connectivity more than ever

now (Ramal, 2022;). The Juglote-Skardu Road project highlights the upgrade, improvement, extension, and further development of the road. The old street that was utilized by explorers to arrive at Skardu was perilous and required local talented drivers due to sharp turns and tight sections. Because of the terrible street conditions, vacationers either favored heading out to Skardu via air or visiting different regions in the north assuming that they were going by street.

Juglote-Skardu Road was first built in 1984 by Frontier Works Organization (FWO). Due to consistent encounters with continuous avalanches and weighty snowfall in the region, the street was harmed tremendously. Considering individuals' advantage in visiting Skardu, traffic on the course and the proportion of consistent deadly mishaps, up-gradation, and augmenting of the street was exceptionally vital to give a protected entry to individuals and vacationers. Considering this course will be a well-known one since it's a traveler's area of interest. Juglote-Skardu Road has been expanded in width from 3.6 meters to 7.3 meters. This will permit a superior and smooth progression of traffic out and about. In addition, the time it took to arrive at Skardu from Gilgit was around 10 hours, which will currently be decreased to four hours (Ali, 2021).

Figure 1 Map of the Study area

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1 Social Capital Theory

Robert D. Putnam, an American political scientist, is also widely recognized for his work on social capital. He wrote a famous book titled "Bowling Alone: The Collapse and Revival of American Community" in 2000, in which he explored the decline of social connectedness in the United States and its consequences for society. Putnam's work helped popularize the concept of social capital and its importance in understanding community and social networks. Social Capital Theory, Social networks, connections, and community ties are important for attaining a variety of goals, including social and economic well-being, according to the sociological and economic theory known as "social capital theory." It implies people can access opportunities, resources, and information through their networks and contacts. The networks, connections, and trust that exist within a community are mentioned to as social capital. Social capital may be impacted by the road's

construction since it will increase connectivity and encourage engagement between underserved groups and the larger society. Examine how social capital shifts within marginalized communities affect the socioeconomic development of those communities.

4. Results

Data were collected from 100 respondents for the study out of which, 56% belonged to the age group 25-45, 10% were 18-24 years old and the remaining 4% of the sampled population belonged to the 46-64 years old age group. The total respondents were male in the survey, where 26% of respondents were illiterate, 5% were primarily passed, 5% were Matric, 18% had secondary education, 6% were undergraduate and 36% of the respondents were master's degree holders. Out of 100 respondents, 14% were Govt employees, 9% were private employees, 57% had their own business and 20% belonged to the farming profession.

Table 1 Socioeconomic and Demographic characteristics

Age		
18 - 24	25- 45	46-64
10%	56%	34%
Education		
Illiterate	26	26%
Primary	5	5%
Matric	9	9%
Higher Secondary	18	18%
Undergraduate	6	6%
Master	36	36%
Occupation		
Business	57	57%
Farmer	20	20%
Govt employ	14	14%
Private employ	9	9%

During the survey, out of 100 respondents, 85 were engaged in indifferent economic generation activities other than their main occupation. Results showed that 29% owned hotels, 20% were associated with the agricultural field, 17% were general store owners, 7% were tour guides, and 3% belonged to dive operations and transportation. The majority of respondents' main activity through JSR was hotel business (Figure

1). Out of 85 respondents, 41% responded that business activities were medium, 27% responded small business activities and 17% gave their consent in favor of large business activities (Figure 3). All the respondents engaged in activities related to business were asked about the number of employees they have hired for their business.

Figure 2 Main activity of Business through JSR

Figure 3 Business classified due to JSR

Respondents were asked about the various listed impacts and were probed to agree or disagree with the arguments if they believed they had impacted their lives. About 99% responded that traffic flow has increased in the area after the construction of JSR. About 80% agreed that their life has been affected by JSR. 51% of individuals responded that all the infrastructural changes have been attributed to their income. Hence, almost more than 70% confirmed that their income has been affected positively impact

through the construction of the JSR. Table 4 demonstrate the impact of JSR on the community through direct and indirectly 99% Increase in travel is the main consequences of JSR that effect the life style infrastructural changes and economy of the community that is the good indicator of this road they may change the life style in the future. Roads can significantly impact a community in various ways, influencing its development, economy, environment, and overall well-being.

Figure 4 Impact of JSR on the Community

Culture changes

Figure 5 the respondents were asked about their perception of the outcomes of JSR. Almost 81 % of the respondents agreed that this project has positive impacts in terms of increasing income and economic activities in the area where cultural and behavioral changes follow development. The highway system caused significant changes to the physical, cultural, and historical landscapes. Out of all the respondents, 89 % agreed that the project would also have an impact on the culture and behavior of the residents. The society takes on new cultural traits, behavior, and social norms, and adopts a new social structure the changes start to occur in the society. 97%

respondents probed Improvement and Up gradation of JSR has reduced travel time for locals and tourists. Efficient roads and transportation networks can reduce travel times between places which will result in higher traffic flow in the area that will further provide new income opportunities for the locals. Understanding how roads impact culture, behavior, and time perception is essential for communities to leverage these effects positively. It allows for the preservation of cultural heritage (Qasim et al., 2024), fostering social connectivity, and shaping sustainable development while acknowledging and respecting the cultural diversity along these pathways.

Figure 5 Benefits through JSR

In Figure 6, the results of the social survey showed that 97 % of the individuals responded that JSR would have a positive impact on the community by providing new business opportunities. Respondents also agreed on the creation of new job opportunities after completion of JSR. A large no of the Local community (57%) was unaware of the Tourist facilitation center while 36 % agreed upon establishing new tourist facilitation centers along JSR for better guidance of tourists in the area. Due to this road the value of goods in the area may be increased. When respondents were asked about dust emission during the construction of JSR, 96 % responded that dust and air pollution was the major problem in future due to bulk vehicular movements and

development Gilgit Baltistan has the fragile ecosystem.

This higher dust emission was due to the topographic features of the area, which is a closed and confined valley. In Figure 6, (66%) of respondents answered that the job creation will be increased and 97% asked that they is good for the local community. On the other hand, poor road infrastructure might isolate communities, limiting interactions and opportunities for cultural exchange. Well-constructed roads improve accessibility, allowing customers, suppliers, and employees to reach businesses more easily. Improved connectivity to markets and transportation hubs facilitates the movement of goods, reducing logistical challenges and costs.

Figure 6 Benefits and emission through JSR

Figure 7 Income of business before and after JSR

Figure 7 summarizes the economic impacts of JSR on the local community. Sampling villagers was plotted along the X-axis while income in PKR was plotted along the Y-axis. It is evident from the figure that the annual income of the local community has increased. From Point 1 to 47 along X-Axis, a sharp increase in income was noted. This sharp increase occurred because this area comes under section I of JSR. This section was completed earlier hence; economic activities have been restored after construction and up-gradation work. The graph from points 47 to 63 depicts section-II and III.

Currently, annual income in these areas has decreased. Some hotels and shops were demolished during the widening and construction of JSR, which has resulted in the decline in reconstruction and development of the hotel industry. It is evident from the figure that the average annual income has been increased, apparently improving the economic flow and well-being of the local community due to improved JSR. Road infrastructure contributes to economic growth by promoting trade and commerce. Improved roads can stimulate business activity, leading to job creation and a more vibrant local economy.

5. Discussions

According to Khadaroo & Neetanah (2007) and Masson & Petiot, (2009), Road infrastructure plays an important role in business and tourism industry development. It has been noticed that the construction of JSR positively affected the locals, especially those belonging to activities related to tourism, and others related to agricultural activities since they got easy access from their farmlands to the market. It was observed that the access enhanced the activities that locals belong to. Road and transport infrastructure provide easy access to tourism and increase business activities in the region having a positive effect on the local community's standard of living.

Scholars have suggested that road and transport infrastructure not only play a vital role in enhancing existing tourism activities, it also promotes the development of new tourism sites in the region (Currie & Falconer, 2014; Musa & Ndawayo, 2011; Virkar and Mallya, 2018; Qasim & Rahman, 2022). Well-developed roads play a significant role in the

economic development of any region. (Ali et al., 2017; Chauvet & Baptiste, 2019). Similar developments have been witnessed due to the construction of JSR. The road project has enhanced the living standards of the locals as an increase in travel has been observed. The movement of individuals in the region and infrastructural changes has increased income and sources of income.

These positive changes have changed the life standards. Exactly 100% of respondents in the study claimed that the economic value of their goods has been increased, which will benefit them in earning handsome money. A study suggested that road and transport infrastructure in a country attracts tourists and can promote tourism destinations (Virkar & Mora, 2018; Qasim et al., 2022). JSR has resulted in increased income generation of the business setups. Both positive and negative trend has been observed here. Most businesses have observed an increase in their annual income. However, those businesses have faced a decline in their business due to short distances and unstopable routes from the city to their destination. In another research, Bhattacharya, Kawai, & Nag, 2012 said that roads and transportation remove poverty by linking remote areas and individuals with main business centers and city markets, and also minimize the development gap in the region.

JSR will pass through these areas and is expected to attract a high number of international tourists. The arrival of a great number of tourists is likely to promote tourism activities in these areas, including the construction of hotels, restaurants, and related businesses (Qasim & Rahman, 2022). Such activities may have a significant impact on the residents living in these areas. Almost 90% of locals in the jurisdiction of JSR believe that JSR may result in cultural and behavioral changes in the region. Responses were recorded that JSR might result in; the society taking on new cultural traits and behavior and social norms etc. whereas it was also noticed that almost all of the individual believe that the change will be good for their community, as it would result in promotion of their culture. Due to the construction of JSR, the tourist influx has increased exponentially, which unintentionally affects the social and cultural life of the local community and inspires them.

Construction of Roads and infrastructure create positive perceptions in the local community around the benefits of tourism, which may subsequently generate positive support in the local community for tourism in the area. The development of road and transport infrastructure may generate a negative environmental impact, such as habitat destruction, traffic congestion, noise, air pollution, and damage to natural beauty. (Kanwal et al., 2019; Nunkoo&Ramkissoon, 2011; Park et al., 2015).

6. Conclusion

Juglote -Skardu Road, the strategic vein and lifeline of Baltistan with about 165 km distance. The road is very important from the business, tourist and also strategic point of view. The central Juglote-Skardu Road connects the Karakoram Highway (KKH). One of the biggest MOUs signed in history between the Gilgit Baltistan Provisional Government and the Federal Government on 1st Nov 2016 and the total cost is 34 billion. JSR makes it easier to access the strategic area linking Pakistan to Saltoro Ridge and the highest battleground on earth. This will not only benefit the tourism industry in the region but also boost the economic potential and cultural diversity of the region. JSR will provide access to basic facilities of life specifically in rural and remote areas of Gilgit Baltistan like Education health tourism and the banking sector. These opportunities will directly or indirectly affect the people of Gilgit Baltistan and will improve their living standards, at the same time there

are possibilities for cultural and behavioral changes in the lives of locals. when transport infrastructure is efficient, it provides various economic and social opportunities and benefits that result in positive multiplier effects such as better accessibility to markets, employment, education, health, and additional investments. The project will also have consequences on the environment; the rise in automobile movement through the road will result in a rise the carbon emissions and will directly cause climate change.

Due to poor road connectivity tourism activities have been limited in these areas in the past. Pakistan has made improvements in the road infrastructure through time for the development of the country as well as the rural areas, China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is an example in this regard which connects China to the Gawadar in Pakistan. The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of the JSR road on Culture, Education, and tourism development in Gilgit Baltistan. This area is full of natural beauty with the world's highest mountain ranges, lakes, glaciers, plateaus, and lush green pastures. The study has shown that the local community has positive perceptions and is ready to provide support for tourism in Gilgit Baltistan. In addition, this study explains the mediating mechanisms in the form of community satisfaction and perceived tourism benefits in the relationship between JSR roads.

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